

WORKSHOP ON IDENTIFICATION OF BARRIERS AND INFORMATION NEEDS FOR ENBIOS MODELLING IN THE CATALAN CASE STUDY

DRAFT V2. JUNE 2023

THIS REPORT DESCRIBES THE METHODS, IMPLEMENTATION AND FINDINGS OF THE WORKSHOP ORGANIZED BY RGI AND UAB ON MARCH 29TH 2023 IN ICTA-UAB, BARCELONA, SPAIN

AUTHORS:

Cristina Madrid López, UAB
Cristina Pérez Sánchez, UAB
Amanda Schibline, RGI
Miquel Sierra Montoya, UAB
Nikki Harasta, UAB
Maria Cassinello, UAB
Ramin Soleymani, UAB
Andrzej Ceglaz, RGI

CONTACT: CRISTINA.MADRID@UAB.CAT

**Funded by
the European Union**

Justwind4all is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European climate, infrastructure and environment executive agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them (grant agreement 101083936).

CONTENTS

CONTENTS	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
BARRIERS TO WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA	4
ENBIOS DEVELOPMENT	5
INTRO.....	6
JUSTWIND4ALL IN A SNAPSHOT	6
WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA	7
WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES AND METHODS	8
OBJECTIVE	8
METHODS	8
WORKSHOP FINDINGS	11
GENERAL BARRIERS TO WIND ENERGY PROJECTS	11
SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA.....	13
PRIORITISATION OF BARRIERS.....	20
ADAPTATION OF ENBIOS	21
SOCIO-ECOLOGICAL ISSUES IN WIND ENERGY MODELLING	21
WHAT IS ENBIOS	22
ENBIOS IN ACTION: ASSESSMENT OF CATALAN SCENARIOS	23
IDENTIFYING POTENTIAL ENBIOS CONTRIBUTIONS	28
ACTION POINTS.....	32
REFERENCES.....	34
ANNEX.....	37
WORKSHOP AGENDA AND FACILITATION GUIDE	37
PARTICIPANT INSTITUTIONS.....	38
PRESENTATIONS.....	38
PICTURES OF WORKSHOP'S MATERIALS	45
ENBIOS SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS.....	47

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The JustWind4All project aims to accelerate the deployment of onshore and offshore wind energy in Europe through effective governance, creating synergies among people and organizations to coordinate and participate in wind energy actions. The project develops knowledge, practical guidelines, instruments, strategies, and training for just and effective decision-making in wind energy governance. One of its key activities is the Wind Forum, a platform designed to engage with local, regional, national and EU wind energy governance actors.

This report covers the results of a workshop entitled "Barriers of Wind Energy in Catalunya and the ENBIOS Socio-Environmental Impact Assessment", held at the Institute for Environmental Science and Technology, in Barcelona in March 2023. The workshop aimed to *identify the parameters that must be included in the ENBIOS tool during its adaptation to the wind energy specifics*. The attendees of the workshop were policy-makers, industry representatives, NGOs, and civil society operating in Catalunya, a case study.

The workshop activities departed from a previous identification of the general barriers to the implementation of wind energy (STEP 1). This was followed by the identification of barriers to both onshore and offshore wind energy that are specific in Catalunya (STEP 2) with an open discussion organized in a World Cafe. Barriers were then prioritized following the Eisenhower matrix of relevance and urgency (STEP3). Finally, the main drivers of the barriers and potential ENBIOS contributions to overcome them were discussed using a two-round process coproduction based on an adaptation of group-level assessment for the 5 barriers that were classified as priorities (STEP 4).

BARRIERS TO WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA

The following barriers were identified in Catalunya:

Administrative Processes. Onshore wind projects exceeding 50 MW are evaluated at the state level, while those below 50 MW are assessed by the Catalan government. The administrative processes involve obtaining permits from three departments - territory, environment, and energy - in several steps. More than half of the onshore wind farm requests evaluated by the Catalan government are still at the initial stages. The lack of clear administrative requirements, subjective criteria for approval, and incoherent guidelines from different administrative departments make the process challenging for project developers. Though the latest revisions to the Decree-Law 16/2019 have incorporated a list of requirements to expedite the process, a high number of approval submissions continues to create a bottleneck. Offshore wind projects are evaluated by the Spanish government only and meet the same barriers and more due to their novelty.

Lack of strategic planning Catalunya lacks an effective planning strategy for the deployment of renewable energy. The uncertainty over future planning poses a challenge to wind energy deployment. Highlighted criteria are territorial balance and biodiversity conservation. There is concern about impacts outside protected areas perceived as acceptable.

Political will Energy transition is currently a priority on the Catalan political agenda, but a political change could call this into question, and a shift to unfavourable policies could become a barrier to the deployment of wind energy.

Social opposition is based on territorial imbalance (concentration of projects in certain areas), lack of perceived benefits, impact on local economic activities, land-use competition with agricultural activities or marine use competition with fisheries, landscape impacts affecting tourism, insufficient local participation in energy decision-making, absence of community engagement, difficulties in the economic participation of local citizens in the projects, lack of awareness of the climate crisis and of the external dependency, policy inconsistencies leading to a lack of systemic transformation, and environmental impacts. Relating to the latter, there is special concern about the cumulative impacts that the projects might have on ecosystems, particularly on birds. The uncertainty over the potential impacts of electromagnetic fields and floating turbines in offshore wind farms, also raises concerns.

Technical issues Due to their technological complexity, offshore wind farms may require the establishment of experimental platforms of considerable duration for testing technological innovations, which may require a considerable duration. In contrast, the technology for onshore wind turbines is well-established as a result of its long-standing implementation. In any case, planning wind farms coherently to facilitate connections to the grid remains a challenge.

ENBIOS DEVELOPMENT

ENBIOS is a python-based tool designed for the assessment the sustainability of energy transition pathways. The purpose of ENBIOS is to compute a set of environmental impact and sustainability indicators of energy transition pathways integrating information and knowledge from two methodologies: life cycle assessment (LCA) and the Multi-Scale Integrated Analysis of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM). We identified the following action points for the development of ENBIOS:

- **Regionalization of results** (using data from the administration and private sector, as well as integrating the zoning maps of MITECO and the Catalan Department of Territory).
- **Inclusion of the local socio-ecological relations** (modelling the impacts at the local level, connecting social dynamics with impacts, and assessing trade-offs between local impacts and regional benefits of wind energy).
- **Addition of metrics for impacts on marine dynamics and biodiversity** Connecting impacts like the wake effect with changes in biodiversity for offshore Improving zoning maps. Creating a variation of current zoning maps which adds to protected areas other relevant information like bird or marine corridors with information from RAMPE and EMODnet.
- **Development of metrics for assessment of impact trade-offs** with a systemic perspective that joints LCA and social-metabolism metrics.
- **Improvement of information transfer** by refining the visualization of results and developing a simplified way of communicating the metrics without reducing them to a single number.

INTRO

JUSTWIND4ALL IN A SNAPSHOT

The transition to renewable energy systems is a key political objective at the European, state, and regional levels that could contribute to an effective climate change mitigation. Apart from this structural aim, in response to Russia's invasion of Ukraine, the European Commission developed the REPowerEU plan to make Europe independent from Russian fossil fuels and to accelerate the clean energy transition (European Commission, 2022). In order to achieve the objectives of REPowerEU, the percentage of domestically-produced renewable energy will need to increase to 45% of the energy supply by 2030, as seen in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. EU RENEWABLE ENERGY TARGETS, INCLUDING REPOWEREU

This will require huge expansions of solar and wind energy capacities. According to the European Commission, 510 GW of wind will be required to reach the 2030 target. This amounts to an average addition of 36 GW of wind energy per year. The implementation of this accelerated wind energy infrastructure is highly dependent on regional and local governance actors. While it is imperative that regional and local governments meet the EU renewable energy targets, it is also integral to have local buy-in to balance social, environmental, economic and technological impacts and benefits.

JustWind4All is a Horizon Europe project that aims to support the acceleration of on- and offshore wind energy, including emerging wind technologies like airborne and floating, through just and effective governance. JustWind4All aims to develop knowledge, practical guidelines, instruments, strategies, and training for just and effective decision-making in onshore and offshore wind energy governance. One of the key activities of the JustWind4All project is engaging with local, regional, national and EU wind energy governance actors across policy, community and industry through its Wind Forum – a platform designed to meet, network, discuss and become agents of action.

To achieve the full potential of both on- and offshore wind energy across Europe in a sustainable manner, JustWind4All addresses four key challenges related to the effective and just governance of wind energy:

To tackle these challenges and advance just, sustainable wind by incorporating multiple approaches, JustWind4All uses a trans-disciplinary multi-method research design and creates synergies among wind energy governance actors to coordinate and participate in actions around wind energy deployment.

From a socio-environmental perspective, the ENBIOS tool, developed by the Institute of Environmental Science and Technology at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (ICTA-UAB), aims to promote holistic energy impact assessment for fit-for-purpose decision-making. The ENBIOS tool has been used to assess the impacts of the energy transition in the European Union, as well as some of the scenarios proposed by the Integrated national energy and climate plan (PNIEC) of the Spanish government. In JustWind4All, ENBIOS will further develop to assess scenarios of wind energy implementation in Catalunya, Bulgaria, and North Holland.

WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA

Catalunya is one of the main case studies in JustWind4All, with a key objective of adapting the ENBIOS tool to regional on- and offshore wind energy realities. Practical knowledge from diverse stakeholders in Catalunya and the South-West European region will be applied to improve the metrics of the ENBIOS tool, making it a more effective tool for energy transition planning and implementation.

Following the European Union (EU) calls for a decarbonization of the energy system through the Energy Union Strategy (COM/2015/080), Spain formalized its Integrated Energy and Climate National Plan 2021-2030 (PNIEC) (MITECO, 2020). The Catalan Government has also presented its own energy transition plan to 2025 or PROENCAT2050 (ICAEN, 2022).

PROENCAT sets the path towards the energy system model in Catalunya and its preliminary version gives an overview of the strategies to be implemented to remove the fossil fuels from the energy system in Catalunya by 2050. This prospective analysis includes a quantitative forecast of the energy supply and demand year by year from 2017 to 2050. In summary, it envisions an increase in efficiency that would result in reduction of total energy demand (-30,7%), while expecting a huge electrification of all economic sectors.

Table 1 presents the installed power and electricity production foreseen by the preliminary version of PROENCAT2050. For simplicity, we have grouped the periods by decade.

TABLE 1. POWER (MW) AND PRODUCTION (GWH) BY TECHNOLOGY - PROENCAT2050

	INSTALLED POWER (MW)				PRODUCTION (GWH)			
	2020	2030	2040	2050	2020	2030	2040	2050
HYDROPOWER	1825,3	1825,8	1825,8	1825,8	5209,6	4438	4358,1	4216,1
WIND ONSHORE	1271,1	5234,2	16939	23136	2637,2	13965,2	37595,7	46710,5
WIND OFFSHORE	0	1000	1500	3500	0	4150	6099,4	13357,7
PHOTOVOLTAIC ROOFTOP	249,7	2185,2	7275,9	11144,4	325,9	3111,6	10360,6	15599,3
PHOTOVOLTAIC OTHERS	0	512,6	2026,6	2614	0	733	2898	3674,5
PHOTOVOLTAIC OPEN-GROUND	94,8	4458,8	13129	19394,3	158,2	7794,5	23125,9	32690,9
OTHER RENEWABLES	116,7	191,8	270,9	247,4	416,6	893,1	1322,7	1223,8
TOTAL	3558	15408	42967	61862	8748	35085	85760	117473
STORAGE	534	2234	4034	7234				
PUMPED HYDRO	534	2034	3534	3734				
BATTERIES	0	200	500	3500				

WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES AND METHODS

This report presents the results of a workshop entitled “Barriers of Wind Energy in Catalunya and the ENBIOS Socio-Environmental Impact Assessment” carried out in person on March 29th 2023 at the Institute of Environmental Science and Technology (ICTA-UAB). All the resulting materials have been digitalized.

OBJECTIVE

This workshop was dedicated to two of the key objectives of the JustWind4All project: (i) increasing engagement linked to effective and just wind energy governance, and (ii) advancing holistic wind energy impact assessment for fit-for-purpose decision-making.

More concretely we aimed to **identify parameters that must be included in the ENBIOS tool during its adaptation to the wind energy specifics.**

Attendants included policy-makers, industry, consultants, NGOs and civil society operating in Catalunya, our case study. They provided practical knowledge on barriers to wind energy deployment in the region. The list of participant institutions can be consulted in the Annex.

METHODS

To reach the definition of metrics, we started with a literature review of the general barriers to the implementation of wind energy, which have been widely assessed (STEP1). This literature review served as preparation to the engagement activities of the workshop in steps 3, 4 and 5. We started by identifying how known barriers are expressed in Catalunya as well as other barriers not previously covered in the literature (STEP2), separating between on and offshore wind energy deployment. As not all barriers can be covered in the modelling at once, we prioritized the list resulting from the World Cafe according to the effect they have in wind energy development and the urgency of solving them (STEP3). We then discussed which information needs would help dealing with those barriers, what metrics

could provide us with this information and what data sources exist to be used in the calculation of metrics. Figure 2 summarizes these four steps.

FIGURE 2. SUMMARY OF THE METHODOLOGY USED IN THE WORKSHOP

STEP 1: LITERATURE REVIEW

We carried out a review of the literature on barriers to wind energy deployment. For this, we identified scientific articles that related to this topic employing Google Scholar as a search engine using the following keywords: “barriers”, “obstacles”, “conflict”, “opposition”, “wind energy”, “wind power”, “wind farms”, “wind development”. The main sources reviewed were scientific articles that documented barriers across the World and a report of a project on renewable energy barriers and best practices in Europe (Banasiak et al., 2022).

STEP 2: ASSESSING BARRIERS TO THE IMPLEMENTATION: WORLD CAFE

We organized an open discussion using the World Cafe methodology to allow intimate yet diverse groups of stakeholders (Brown & Isaacs, 2005). The literature review showed that there is an important distinction between the barriers to the implementation of onshore and offshore energy projects. We then included this distinction in the identification of barriers. Participants were separated in two tables, one for onshore and another one for offshore barrier discussions, keeping diversity of affiliations.

Each table had one question only: “what are the barriers to the implementation of (off/onshore) wind energy deployment in Catalunya?”. The question was kept purposefully open to allow for any type of barrier to come up. Each table had one facilitator and one note taker. Even though we had originally planned two 30 minute rounds with change of participants, the discussions were fruitful and we decided to allow a 60 minute round without participant change. Discussions took place in Catalan, mostly, and some translation was necessary for the colleagues of the organization that did not speak the language.

STEP 3: PRIORITISATION OF BARRIERS

The World Cafe resulted in a broad network of barriers, we needed to understand which ones were a priority for the project. Our prioritisation activity was inspired by an adaptation

of the Eisenhower matrix that divides items in four quadrants: urgent and important, urgent but not important, not urgent but important, and not urgent and not important.

The objective of this exercise was to assess the barriers according to two criteria: (1) the effect of not-addressing of a given barrier on the implementation of wind power (the vertical axis) and (2) the urgency of addressing a given barrier to progress with the wind power development (the horizontal axis). Our aim was not to unambiguously decide whether some of the barriers are more important than others, as all of them have an impact on wind power development and should be addressed and, eventually, overcome. Instead, the goal of this session was to understand from a comparative perspective, which of the barriers shall be prioritized by the JW4A team to include in the next steps of the project's development.

An additional objective of this session was to allow the participating stakeholders to confront their priorities regarding addressing different wind power development barriers with other participants, generating an additional space for discussion, and allowing them to collectively reflect on the different perceptions represented by other actors.

This session was structured as follows: the facilitator selected a first, random barrier of the wind power development and suggested when it should be placed between the two axes. This suggestion was discussed by the stakeholders and, if needed, adjusted. After the agreement, another barrier was selected and the facilitator suggested where it should be placed in this framework, considering the previously placed barrier. This move was again discussed by the stakeholders, until reaching an agreement. This exercise was repeated using most of the barriers discussed during the World Cafe. If needed, the barriers placed in the framework in the previous rounds, have been moved around to reflect the stakeholders' perspectives to the most accurate extent.

STEP 4: IDENTIFICATION OF INFORMATION NEEDS

As commented above, the further step of including the barriers into the modelling process is not straightforward and there are few studies that have done so. We used an adaptation of the methods developed in Süsser et al. (Süsser et al., 2021) to assess information needs and transform it into the QTDIAN toolbox, a set of parameters that can be included in energy modelling to consider a particular narrative. Figure 3 shows the original method and our adaptation.

The creation of the QTDIAN toolbox was also based on the information needs of different public who uses either the models or the results of models. However, the previous discussion to identify information needs was based in the questions "how do you see the future energy system?" and "what do we need to get there?". As a reminder we are processing barriers identified with the questions expressed above "what are the barriers to the implementation of (off/onshore) wind energy deployment in Catalunya?". Once the information needs are identified a further work of metric definition and data collection was carried out to build the tables that form the QTDIAN toolbox.

In our case, we followed a two-round process coproduction based on an adaptation of group-level assessment (Vaughn & Lohmueller, 2014) for the 5 barriers that were classified as priorities in step 3. The first round consisted in the individual identification and presentation of barrier drivers and related metric for each of the five barriers that were considered a priority. In a second round these proposals were discussed to find consensus about the definition of metrics. Participants also provided us with some leads on data sources that

would be relevant to define these metrics. The resulting metrics and data are to be included in ENBIOS and would result in the development of new methods when necessary.

FIGURE 3. ADAPTATION OF THE QTDIAN METHOD

WORKSHOP FINDINGS

GENERAL BARRIERS TO WIND ENERGY PROJECTS

Current climate and energy policies envision a rapid deployment of renewable energy sources to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. At many governmental levels, (European, Spanish, Catalan), wind energy is considered a crucial energy source in this endeavor, as it can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase energy security. However, studies have shown that even though the position of general public about wind energy tends to be positive, the list of failed wind energy projects keeps growing (Devine-Wright, 2011). In this section we summarize the most important barriers covered in the literature.

Administrative processes play a critical role in the deployment of renewable energy technologies (Darmani et al., 2014). According to a recent study, inadequate authorization and permission procedures represent the most widespread barrier for renewable energy sources in Europe, affecting more than 95% of European countries (Banasiak et al., 2022). The three main issues related to this topic are the complexity, the duration and the lack of transparency of administrative procedures for planning and permitting. These processes are complex and require the approval of several administrations at different levels (national, regional, local), which are often uncoordinated (Iglesias et al., 2011). This represents a considerable bureaucratic red tape (Martin & Rice, 2015) leading to lengthy procedures that entail significant transaction costs (Banasiak et al., 2022). In addition, many countries lack pre-defined criteria for administrative approvals. This enables policy-makers to be influenced in their decisions by personal interests. The absence of criteria undermines transparency, which results in unsuccessful investors not knowing why they have not been selected, as the scores of each participant in the contests are not published. The lack of clear criteria, weights, and scores might enhance legal disputes, delaying the deployment of wind projects (Iglesias et al., 2011).

Technical barriers, which represented an important obstacle some decades ago, are fading over time, as the wind industry becomes more mature and competitive (Smit et al., 2007). Nevertheless, some technical challenges remain, especially regarding new technologies, such as floating and airborne wind technologies (Cortese, 2019; Subbulakshmi et al., 2022). Because of the complexity of wind energy deployment, a considerable volume of skilled personnel is necessary to implement and maintain wind farms, including researchers, engineers, trainers, technicians and policy analysts. For this reason, the shortage of specialized wind energy staff and the absence of adequate training programs has been identified as a barrier to the diffusion of this kind of energy (Friebe et al., 2014). The main technical challenge today is due to the intermittent nature of wind energy, which leads to a less predictable electricity supply and difficulties in the management of grids (Georgilakis, 2008). This is an important challenge due to the need to achieve grid stability and supply-demand coupling. Insufficient grid capacity and extension can pose a threat to the construction of wind farms, but grid reinforcement has been affected by technical challenges, a lack of development plans, administrative processes, and excessive implementation costs (Banasiak et al., 2022; Hammons, 2008).

Economic and market barriers also present fundamental obstacles for the wind industry (Diógenes et al., 2020). Wind technology costs have been rapidly declining over the course of the past decade, making this technology more economically viable. Yet, wind farm projects still present high up-front costs, requiring significant initial capital and credit accessibility (Dhingra et al., 2022). Access to finance is hindered by other pre-existing issues, such as a lack of stable support schemes, inadequate subsidies, and power pricing schemes (Banasiak et al., 2022). Similarly, several market-related barriers hold back the deployment of wind energy. The dominance of some conventional retailers and energy utilities constitutes an obstacle to fair and independent renewable energy markets (Banasiak et al., 2022). These barriers suppose an even higher for small wind energy cooperative projects.

Social acceptance is identified in the literature as a powerful barrier to the diffusion of wind energy, due to its ability to slow down, or even stop the implementation of wind farms (Devine-Wright, 2005; Toke et al., 2008). In the last decades, there has been an outstanding emergence of associations at multiple levels (from local to national) that strongly oppose renewable projects at the macro-scale (Moragues-Faus & Ortiz-Miranda, 2010). Contestations articulate through three major issues: the unfair distribution of costs and benefits of energy transitions; the disregard for alternative landscape valuations and the insufficient local participation in energy planning (Zografos & Martinez-Alier, 2009). On the third issue, although energy plans and projects generally fulfill the necessary legal requirements for stakeholder consultation during their environmental impact assessment, local community members often claim that they are not effectively engaged in energy planning (Duarte et al., 2022a), which results in policies that fail to recognize their concerns and preferences (Aitken et al., 2008).

An unbalanced territorial distribution of energy production infrastructure has also been identified as a critical issue that hinders local acceptance. Although energy generation facilities have been promoted as a potentially significant new source of jobs and rural development (OECD, 2012), their socio-economic and demographic benefits can be difficult to achieve in rural territories, with only temporary job creation and a lack of success in retaining population (Duarte et al., 2022b). This adds to existing conflicts between the preservation of lands with high agricultural value and the massive expansion of renewable energy (Poggi et al., 2018), which often results in increased farmland prices (Haan & Simmler, 2018; Myrna et al., 2019). Local mobilizations against wind farms are also due to

the ecological impacts that a large-scale deployment have on valuable species and habitats, and concerns regarding cumulative effects, as these facilities coexist with other impacting economic activities and infrastructure (Lloret et al., 2022; Maxwell et al., 2022).

These barriers are not homogeneously distributed. In some cases, the technical aspects play a major role whereas in others the main barrier may be social opposition, which in itself can be explained by NIMBYism or not (Devine-Wright, 2005). This is why it is important to assess the barriers for each specific case.

SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA

During the World Cafe session, participants shared constructive and valuable knowledge regarding the implementation barriers for both onshore and offshore wind energy. After grouping together and further analyzing the feedback received, key insights from the discussion are presented below.

ONSHORE WIND

Table 2 summarizes the results from the onshore table at the World Cafe.

BARRIER 1: ADMINISTRATIVE PROCESSES

Participants agreed that administrative processes for wind energy projects are long and slow. They explained that there are three administrative areas in charge of permitting: territory, environment, and energy; and several steps to obtain all necessary permits. More than half of the requests get stuck in the initial stages of the procedure, when the report on the sufficiency and suitability of the submitted documentation is issued. The projects that pass this stage need to process the documentation an average of 2.3 times.

Project developers thought that the list of administrative requirements was not clear, therefore the last modification of the Decree-Law 16/2019, of November 26, on urgent measures for the climate emergency and the promotion of renewable energies, added an annex with the list of the requirements of the different administrations.

Another issue identified is the lack of objective criteria for administrative approval, administrations must decide project by project, instead of having a set of criteria that accelerate the process. Developers also complain about the incoherence of criteria for projects, which results in different administrative departments giving contradictory guidelines, making developers re-design projects several times.

The administrative process has been simplified with a single phase of public exposure, but permitting still presents a bottleneck because there is an avalanche of projects (41 wind farm projects submitted in 2022-23 in Catalunya).

BARRIER 2: SOCIAL OPPOSITION

In the last decades, the development of wind energy was mainly hindered by economic and administrative barriers. Now, the social opposition to wind energy is becoming more prominent and is posing a challenge to its development. The following paragraphs will discuss the various factors contributing to social opposition and a few potential solutions identified by the workshop participants.

Territorial imbalance: Energy production facilities have been disproportionately distributed across the territory, with some rural counties in Southern Catalunya concentrating most of the energy infrastructure. Some participants expressed their concerns over this issue, claiming that although the transition to renewable forms of energy has been promoted as a potential source of jobs and rural development, this had not been the case for Catalunya, where rural areas are suffering the cost of the transition, without receiving its benefits. A double territorial imbalance was identified in Catalunya: the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona (AMB) vs the rest of the Catalan territory, as well as the coast vs inland Catalunya. The participants understood that wind farms could only be located where there is wind resource, and in the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona the wind is not strong enough, nonetheless, this area could contribute more with solar power. One reason behind this uneven distribution is the price of land, wind farm developers prefer to establish their projects in remote rural areas where land rent prices are significantly lower. It was discussed that this territorial imbalance was not only related to energy, but rather represents an urban-rural dichotomy, in which rural areas are perceived as the providers of all kinds of resources for the cities.

TABLE 2. SPECIFIC BARRIERS, ONSHORE WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA

BARRIER	SPECIFIC EXPRESSION IN CATALUNYA
Administrative Process	Administrative processes for wind energy projects are slow.
	Developers often present uncompleted documentation, as the list of requirements for the different administrations is not clear. This issue was addressed with the latest revision of Decree-Law 16/2019 which incorporated a list of requirements.
	There is a lack of objective criteria for administrative approval, administrations decide project by project.
	Administrations are not sufficiently coordinated and sometimes give contradictory guidelines.
Social Opposition	<p>Social opposition to wind energy is becoming a barrier to its development. Several factors contribute to this resistance, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wind farms are unevenly distributed across the territory, with some rural areas suffering most of the impacts, without receiving enough benefits. • Renewable energy facilities compete with agricultural activities and raise land prices. • Wind farms significantly alter local landscapes. • There is insufficient local participation in energy projects and a lack of community engagement. • There is a lack of awareness of the climate crisis, and a lack of understanding the impacts of the actual energy model and of our external dependency. • Current policies do not envision a systemic transformation. Opponents to the massive wind energy deployment ask for energy degrowth first.
Political will	Energy transition is currently a priority on the political agenda, but a political change could call this into question.
Lack of strategic planning	Catalunya lacks an effective planning strategy for the deployment of renewable energy.

	Planning should incorporate objective criteria, considering territorial balance and biodiversity conservation.
	There is a need to update protection schemes. The Catalan government wants to advance “less but better protection”.

Land use conflicts: As the production of food and energy is concentrated in the same areas, which are rural territories, land use conflicts appear. Participants identified a clash between energy and food sovereignty, as renewable energy plants were competing with agricultural activities for land. One participant said that this was mostly a problem with solar energy and stated that “Wind energy does not occupy territory, it occupies landscape but not territory”. However, it was also discussed that wind farm developers could pay significantly more for the rent of land than farmers, which was leading to an increase in the price of land. The establishment of energy facilities in areas of high agricultural value is due to the undervaluation of agriculture. The incoherences in the agri-food system were also mentioned: as Catalan lands are producing food to export, energy facilities might not be competing with food sovereignty.

Landscape: Another reason for social opposition is the potential of wind farms to alter the landscape. One participant said that there was no strategy to reduce this impact, as monumentation does not work with wind turbines. However, it was suggested that if the community participates, the perception of the landscape is not the same.

Insufficient local participation: The social resistance to wind energy is also related to the scarce territorial dialogue that exists and the lack of community engagement. Energy policies are designed in the cities, following a top-down planning approach, and therefore they feel imposed to local communities. One participant expressed that the defense of the territories, which is being channeled by platforms such as Aliente and the Xarxa per la Sobirania Energètica, is important to evidence these discomforts. Workshop participants acknowledged that most project developers are failing to connect with local residents, and it was discussed that economic compensation is not enough. Participants called for more wind energy community projects that allow locals to retain the benefits produced by the wind farms, which otherwise are perceived to be appropriated by big companies.

Lack of awareness of the climate and energy crisis: Participants recognized that the social rejection to renewable energy sources evidences the absence of awareness of the climate emergency. The poor understanding of the impacts of the current energy system, of the external dependency and energy insecurity drives the opposition to new energy projects. It was discussed that the current energy system is delocalized, meaning that the impacts of our energy consumption are mostly felt in other territories, where the energy is produced. It was also emphasized that energy systems will always have impacts, and the key was to compare the effects of different energy configurations. Participants acknowledged that cooperative projects could be an effective way to raise awareness. Through cooperative projects, participants said, people can learn more about the effects of their own energy consumption and how it affects the environment, which in turn increases social acceptance of wind energy projects.

Lack of systemic transformation: Participants complained about the lack of coherence among policy measures and argued that the ambitious deployment of renewable energy plans should be accompanied by energy-saving measures. People will not accept that the impacts of large renewable energy facilities are socialized, as long as we keep enlarging airports and having no limits to private vehicles, among other inconsistencies. In this line,

one participant said that changing energy production technologies was not enough, that some actors will continue to contest large energy projects if an energy degrowth perspective was not considered. Another participant said that the reduction in demand is already given by the energy transition, it will occur thanks to a higher efficiency. PROENCAT2050 (the Catalan energy prospective for 2050) plans to lower energy consumption by half, which is to be achieved by electrifying and decarbonizing.

BARRIER 3: POLITICAL WILL

Some participants commented that the energy transition is a priority on the political agenda. Current policies at the European, state and regional level aim to decarbonize our energy systems through a rapid increase in the production of renewable energy. However, participants warned that a political change could call this into question. Other political parties could take over the social opposition to renewable energy infrastructures to halt the energy transition. Conversely, another participant said that political will is a current barrier in Catalunya, as the government is not explaining in a very ambitious way what we have to do with the energy system, why we have to do it and what will happen if we don't do it.

BARRIER 4: LACK OF STRATEGIC PLANNING

It was discussed that Catalunya lacked an effective planning strategy for the deployment of renewable energy. Participants agreed that planning was a difficult endeavor, and it should be approached with the maximum objectivity, establishing a set of criteria to guide decision-making. They mentioned the need to update planning with a better understanding of the impacts and benefits of energy infrastructure. According to participants, two main aspects that should be integrated in planning are territorial balance and biodiversity conservation. Participants declared that protection schemes might be misleading, as they created a territorial dichotomy that led to the understanding that outside protected areas there are no restraints for energy infrastructure. It was said that about 60% of the Catalan territory had some kind of protection figure, but this protection was not effective for conservation purposes. Now, the Catalan government prefers to “advance less but with better protection”. A new territorial plan (PLATTER for the acronym in Spanish) is currently under development.

A key example that guided this discussion was the cooperative project “Viure de l’Aire de Barcelona”, which aims to install one or two wind turbines in Collserola. As it is a protected area, the installation of energy infrastructure is forbidden within the park, but some participants defended that a small wind energy project there would do more good than harm. The project would help territorial balance, bringing some of the cost of energy production to the city of Barcelona, and would raise awareness among its citizens, starting conversations about the energy transition within urban areas. However, another participant expressed his concerns over the fact that Barcelona did not have enough wind, therefore building a wind turbine in this area would produce little energy at the expense of the biodiversity of the Collserola park.

Again, it was mentioned that planning should not be done from the top down, but with stakeholder engagement from the very beginning. This would help reduce the uncertainty felt at the local level and diminish social opposition.

OFFSHORE WIND

Table 3 summarizes the results from the offshore table at the World Cafe.

TABLE 3. SPECIFIC BARRIERS, OFFSHORE WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA

BARRIER	SPECIFIC EXPRESSION IN CATALUNYA
Regulatory Framework and Administrative Process	<p>The uncertainty over the future regulatory framework poses a challenge to offshore wind energy deployment. For example, offshore wind developers have had to plan their projects before the recent approval of the Spanish Maritime Spatial Plan (POEM), which might have led them to undervalue the environmental impacts</p> <p>Administrative processes are slow, due to the lack of experience in offshore wind, the deficit of administrative personnel and the lack of effective coordination between different administrative bodies</p>
Social opposition	<p>Social opposition to offshore wind farms centers around three axes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental impacts: Offshore wind farms might cause severe impacts on marine species. However, offshore wind technology is advancing much faster than the knowledge about environmental impacts. Specially there is lack of information regarding the cumulative impacts on ecosystems, the potential impacts of electromagnetic fields and floating turbines. Data and information on impacts is not effectively shared. • Direct impact on local economic sectors: offshore wind farms might impact local economic activities, mainly tourism and fisheries. • Lack of stakeholders' participation: there is an urgent need to include mechanisms for the participation of citizens and local communities in wind projects at early planning stages. Co-designing plans and projects with the stakeholders involved, would decrease tensions and lead to higher chances of success. Economic participation from local citizens would also be beneficial, but it remains challenging considering the high capital volume that these projects entail.
Technical issues	<p>Due to their technological complexity, offshore wind farms may require the establishment of experimental platforms for testing technological innovations (such as floating platforms), which may require a considerable duration. Furthermore, planning offshore wind farms coherently to facilitate connections to the grid remains a challenge.</p>

BARRIER 1: REGULATORY FRAMEWORK AND ADMINISTRATIVE PROCESSES

Spain has recently approved its own Maritime Spatial Plans (POEM for its acronym in Spanish), which is the law calling for a sustainable development of maritime uses. Representatives from the electricity grid operator and wind industry in Spain present at the table expressed concerns about the slow development of this law. These long delays and lack of experience in offshore wind development in Spain led them to progress with the offshore planning without a clear understanding of what the regulatory framework was going to be, hardening their work. According to environmental conservation NGOs at the table, working without a developed regulation may encourage the wind industry to focus exclusively on the techno-economic aspects of the project and undervalue the environmental impacts that the development of projects could cause on all species present in the marine environment. Therefore, all actors at the table agreed that timely regulation is necessary to clearly define the limits and procedures of marine wind development. Additionally, environmental associations expressed their concerns about creating a regulatory framework that favors the interests of large offshore wind developers. They consider that part of the problem is related to the wind development model itself, as it promotes huge economic benefits for large companies. In this sense, the Catalan Government stipulates that all wind projects in Catalunya must offer a participation of at least 30% of the financing to smaller actors. However, this participation is voluntary, and projects can move forward without it.

Participants noted a lack of experience in developing offshore wind in Spain compared to other European countries. However, despite little experience with administrative processes related to offshore projects, this barrier was also discussed based on experiences with onshore wind development. It was generally agreed that there is a lack of coordination between different administrative bodies, resulting in slower processes than necessary. Additionally, participants emphasized a misalignment between governments' urgency in transitioning to renewable energy and the personnel and resources they allocate to solve related administrative procedures. Consequently, wind energy projects can take as long as 10 years to finally be implemented.

BARRIER 2: SOCIAL OPPOSITION

The discussion on social acceptance of offshore wind power centered around two real-life cases. First, the Tramuntana wind farm, planned to be in the Gulf of Roses, in the northwest of Catalunya, about 16 km from the coast. Second, Portugal's general goal of deploying 10 GW of offshore wind power by 2030. In both cases, the discussion brought to light three main concepts around which social opposition might be organized: environmental impacts, direct impact on local economic sectors, and the lack of participation from citizens and local stakeholders.

Environmental impacts

Among the participants joining the discussions at this table, there was consensus about the lack of information regarding the cumulative impacts that offshore wind power development may have on ecosystems. It was pointed out that technology is advancing much faster than knowledge about environmental impacts. At the same time, the knowledge on environmental impacts gathered in the North Sea, with many years of experience in the development of offshore wind power, can serve to fill this gap. However, there is a lack of data sharing at different levels within the decision-making chain.

According to the participants, there are two particular topics where there is currently most uncertainty due to information gaps are. These are: (1) the potential effects of electromagnetic fields from underground cables, and (2) how different types of foundations might affect marine species. There is also very little information available on floating wind power, which is expected to become very relevant in the sector in a few years. Therefore, the integration of preventive measures to minimize or avoid impacts on marine species corridors is even more challenging. The potential impacts on birds were also widely discussed. From the nature conservation representatives, it was pointed out that the special protection areas (SPAs) for birds (ZEPAs for its acronym in Spanish) cover an insufficient area in Spain. In the case of the Tramuntana parc, they mentioned that the Costa Brava is a critical feeding area for specific bird species.

To conclude, there was a consensus among the stakeholders that environmental impacts should be considered as early as possible in project planning, as it is much more difficult to consider them afterwards. Additionally, there will always be environmental impacts on ecosystems to some extents, so a balance must be aimed between energy needs and environmental and maritime space protection.

Direct impact on local economic sectors

Several stakeholders remarked that the leading voices against the Costa Brava wind park represent different local economic activities and sectors that might be affected by the deployment of the offshore windmills. These include companies related to tourism industry, ports and harbors and fishers. The main arguments of the tourism industry representatives are related to the potential noise, and, especially, to the landscape change that the windmills might produce. Tourism is one of the most important economic sectors in Costa Brava and its key assets lie in the region's promotion as a destination with pristine nature, offering forests, coastal trails, and water-based activities. Therefore, the tourism industry representatives believe windmills might damage this area and its features. Representatives of fisheries are concerned about how offshore wind will affect fish captures, which because of the overfishing and worsening environmental conditions, are already declining. Participants agreed that fisheries opposition is not typical only for Catalunya, but represents a barrier to offshore wind power deployment also in Portugal and across European seas. A possible strategy to deal with this issue would be to place windmills in less profitable places for fishers and use the infrastructure to build aquaculture sites, as was pointed out by participants.

Lack of participation from citizens and local stakeholders in planning

Currently, there is not a collaborative approach in offshore planning starting from day one and this creates tensions and differences that sometimes are impossible to overcome at a late stage. In fact, the information between stakeholders is usually not shared or misinformed. An example of this is the offshore planning in Portugal, where a working group was created, leaving out local stakeholders and conservationists. All participants agreed that there is an urgent need to include citizens and local stakeholders' participation at early planning stages. This means not only to listen to their opinion as outsiders but to include them in decision-making and advocate for co-creation methods. Administrations should try to bring together all the stakeholders involved, which would dramatically increase the chances of the project to succeed.

Despite the consensus, there was a concern on how to concretize this participation. Additionally, economic participation from citizens and local stakeholders was seen as very

challenging considering the complex financial schemes and capital volume that these projects entail.

BARRIER 3: TECHNICAL ISSUES

Offshore wind parks' complexity is higher than that of onshore parks, both on technological and time of development terms. The representative from the electricity grid operator expressed the concern about planning offshore wind farms coherently to facilitate the connections to grid. There shouldn't be one cable for each project, but instead, projects should share part of the grids and the connection points for economic, technical and environmental reasons. Another point that was raised on the table was the need to set experimental platforms to test technological solutions regarding grid tests or new foundation concepts.

PRIORITISATION OF BARRIERS

Figure 4 shows the results of the prioritization exercise. Generally, the stakeholders prioritised several barriers as time-sensitive and having a significant effect on the implementation success of wind energy project development, contributing to a large cluster of barriers in the upper left corner of the matrix. The barrier with the largest effect on implementation that should be addressed in the least amount of time is the lack of sufficient and meaningful public participation for wind energy development in Catalunya.

FIGURE 4. RESULTS OF THE PRIORITIZATION OF BARRIERS

This was followed by interconnected barriers, which are the lack of effective regulation, technical constraints such as wind energy's connection to the electricity grid and the lack of local benefits for communities affected by wind energy. Indeed, the lack of planning, especially in areas with fast wind development, was reported as the second main concern. These prioritisations show the need for a transdisciplinary approach to tackling just wind energy development, including political, social and technical aspects.

When asked to prioritise environmental barriers, the experts did not agree on the level of effect on implementation and when to address the barrier. This was a difficult task as some of them acknowledged a lack of technical knowledge. Some NGO experts argued for the impact on birds and soil to be addressed quicker than other experts. In this context, environmental barriers were placed in the middle of the matrix. The socio-environmental barrier of lack of awareness of citizens in the climate crisis, in contrast, was a very timely barrier to address, while the effect on implementation was still considered only moderate.

Finally, the prioritisation of barriers from a sectoral view was considerably diverse. When considering the barrier of fisheries in offshore wind energy development, the experts ranked fisheries as a very time-sensitive topic to address, but their effect on implementation would be minimal. In contrast, the experts did not think that tourism was time-sensitive, which could also signal why the barrier of visual impacts was similarly low in the matrix. When considering both administrative and technical workforce barriers, the experts also did not prioritise either in terms of time or their effect on implementation.

ADAPTATION OF ENBIOS

SOCIO-ECOLOGICAL ISSUES IN WIND ENERGY MODELLING

The transition to more sustainable energy systems requires large reductions in greenhouse gas emissions. Energy system modelling is used in decision-making processes to define optimum pathways according to an objective of emissions, but also economic costs and energy supply. Other environmental parameters beyond GHG emissions are typically not considered. This oversight can result in non-optimal outcomes in proposed transition pathways and in failed implementation of energy projects.

Indeed, these other environmental parameters may either represent a barrier to the implementation themselves or be the foundation of a social or economic barrier as presented above. Therefore, the consideration in energy modelling of the barriers to the implementation of energy projects in general and of wind projects in particular is important. Still, social and ecological parameters/barriers are rarely considered in energy modelling (Süsser et al., 2022) even though they can significantly change the results of the modelling (Süsser, Pickering, et al., 2021).

The lack of inclusion of these parameters is not so much related to the lack of environmental and social models and studies of energy issues, which are prolific. Scopus reports almost 95 thousand works with the search »energy, environmental impacts« of which 40 thousand are from the field of sustainability science and 9 thousand are from social sciences. The problem is more related to the lack of link between energy models and these types of studies, for which a few tools have been developed.

ENBIOS (Environmental and Bioeconomic System Analysis) (Madrid-López et al., 2022) is an assessment tool that integrates life cycle assessment (LCA) and socio-ecosystem metabolism to provide a comprehensive analysis of the socioecological impacts of energy transition pathways. ENBIOS allows for the evaluation of alternative energy scenarios, the identification of trade-offs and synergies between environmental and bioeconomic goals, and the exploration of policy options for sustainable energy transitions.

ENBIOS has been developed in projects SENTINEL and SEEDS with a generalist approach, including many energy technologies and related impacts with a low resolution. The tool

assesses impacts such as GHG emissions, land and water use, land and water degradation or biodiversity loss. In JUSTWIND4ALL, we will increase the resolution of onshore, offshore and new wind energy technologies and create new methods for their specific impacts.

A first step towards this adaptation requires to understand the barriers to the implementation of wind energy projects, which will point us in the direction of which metrics and methods must be considered in ENBIOS, for it to be relevant for the decision-making process.

WHAT IS ENBIOS

ENBIOS is modelled in a software system in python. Its first version was developed within the EU Horizon 2020 project SENTINEL, but it has been further developed within the CHIST-ERA project SEEDS, the project LIVEN and the Horizon Europe project JUSTWIND4ALL.

The purpose of ENBIOS is to compute a set of environmental impact and sustainability indicators by building a module that relates the various sources of energy within a system to the pressures caused by the technologies that provide them, integrating information and knowledge from three methodologies: life cycle assessment (LCA), the Multi-Scale Integrated Analysis of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM) method and the dynamic simulation-optimization of energy networks.

Figure 5 shows the inputs and outputs provided by ENBIOS. The main functions of ENBIOS include 2 steps to prepare LCA into a NIS compatible format, followed by the main execution. The complete manual can be read [HERE](#).

FIGURE 5. STRUCTURE OF THE ENBIOS SOFTWARE

The key data inputs to most ENBIOS-based investigations will be provided by life cycle assessment (LCA) information. Two fundamental types of LCA inputs are required to prepare a simulation of ENBIOS. Data from the ‘spold’ files that define the inventories at each of the energy-related processes within the system can be converted into a NIS-compatible summary file.

Within the LCA field, inventory data provided within LCI listings for individual processes can be converted into final indicators by using “methods” that apply various characterization factors to each inventory item. To integrate the chosen LCIA methods into ENBIOS calculations, an action is required to convert the raw LCIA method information – available alongside Ecoinvent database sources (Ecoinvent, 2021).

The structure of the system (known as a “dendrogram”) can then be used within a MuSIASEM framework to elaborate indicators that can be manipulated to provide deeper understandings of the inner functions of the system at various levels. It allows the user to assess and compare the consequences that relate to the various elements within an energy system in a way that allows a better understanding and method of comparison for a range of future climate policy scenarios.

ENBIOS IN ACTION: ASSESSMENT OF CATALAN SCENARIOS

We show a brief application of ENBIOS to the assessment of PROENCAT2050 as an example of its potential contribution. We completed a comparison between the PROENCAT 2050 scenarios and the baseline year 2020 (ICAEN, 2020).

Settings

Our analysis covers the impacts of electricity production technologies including the full life cycle of technologies: raw material extraction, manufacturing, transport, installation, use and maintenance, and end-of-life treatments.

TABLE 4. ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES AND POWER SHARES OF THE 2020 SCENARIO¹

ENERGY TYPE	TECHNOLOGY	POWER SHARE (%)	DATA SOURCE
Wind	<1 MW turbines	6,5	(Asociación Empresarial Eólica, n.d.; ICAEN, n.d.)
	1-3 MW turbines	93,5	(Asociación Empresarial Eólica, n.d.; ICAEN, n.d.)
	>3 MW turbines	0	(Asociación Empresarial Eólica, n.d.; ICAEN, n.d.)
Rooftop photovoltaic	Monocrystalline silicon	44,5	(Wernet et al., 2016)
	Polycrystalline silicon	55,5	(Wernet et al., 2016)
Hydropower	Reservoir	88,2	(ICAEN, 2020)
	Run-of-river	11,8	(ICAEN, 2020)
Other renewables ²	Renewable Urban Solid Waste	22,4	(ICAEN, 2020)
	Biogas	53,4	(ICAEN, 2020)
	Biomass	3,4	(ICAEN, 2020)
	Solar Thermolectric	20,8	(ICAEN, 2020)

¹Methodological note. We considered ‘other photovoltaic’ inside open-ground photovoltaic category due to a lack of data. We expect this assumption not having a huge influence in the results since the share of ‘other photovoltaic’ installed power is minimal in all scenarios.

²Although PROENCAT2050 also mentions co-generation with renewables, we left it out due to its minimum relevance in the current power structure in Catalunya (2020).

Table 4 covers the technology disaggregation and their assumed share, according to literature. The general assumptions and calculation methods of future scenarios (2030, 2040 and 2050) as well as the internal structuring of the energy system in ENBIOS is covered in the annex.

RESULTS

One of the added values of ENBIOS is the assessment of the planned installations with a life cycle perspective. This allows us to estimate the impacts of the full value chain, including the impacts of building the infrastructure necessary for the transition to a renewable-based electricity system.

BASELINE YEAR

In this example, we show the results for the accumulated contribution to global warming of the full value chain (GWP100) and the disaggregation for each of the components of the electricity system. Figure 9 shows the 2020 results that are related to infrastructure building and the actual electricity production phase, respectively.

As seen in Figure 6 (above), the CO₂ emissions of the renewable energy-built infrastructure to date is larger (69%) than that of the non-renewable infrastructure (31%). This difference can be explained due to the high contribution of hydropower to the renewable electricity mix (51%). The hydropower infrastructure accounts 50% of the total infrastructure emissions. The second largest infrastructure contributors are nuclear power plants, which represent the 21% of the total emissions and the 67% of the non-renewable emissions. Again, this contribution might be explained due to the large share of nuclear power (28%) of the total power installed in Catalunya. Moreover, this infrastructure has large cement requirements, a CO₂ intensive industry.

Figure 6 (below) shows the GWP100 indicator of the electricity production in 2020. In this case, non-renewable energies dominate the emissions, which represent a 95% of the total. Although they only produce the 11% and 12% of the total electricity production in Catalunya, respectively, cogeneration and combined cycled technologies are the main responsible of the total emissions. This can be explained due to their direct emissions during the use phase, where the combustion takes place.

FIGURE 6. GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL OF BUILDING THE INFRASTRUCTURE (ABOVE) AND ELECTRICITY GENERATION (BELOW). 2020

EVOLUTION OF IMPACTS: INFRASTRUCTURE VS GENERATION

Besides contribution to global warming, ENBIOS can estimate another 15 indicators of environmental impacts. In here we present results for Agricultural Land Occupation (LOP), and Water Consumption Potential (WCP).

Figure 7 above shows the estimated evolution of impacts of the projected cumulative infrastructure with two level of disaggregation. The upper graphs show the difference between renewables and non-renewables, whereas the lower graphs show the disaggregation by technology. Our calculations show an increase of the impacts for the three indicators, mostly due to the installation of photovoltaic technologies. This result is unexpected given that the projected photovoltaic capacity installed is just slightly higher than that of the wind technologies in 2030 and 2040 scenarios. However, the GWP100 per MW installed of a solar photovoltaic silicon monocrystalline is around 2.5 times higher than that of a wind turbine of more than 3 MW.

In the case of agricultural land occupation (LOP), the contribution of photovoltaic technologies is even larger in comparison to wind. The reason for this phenomenon can be attributed to the prevalence of open-ground photovoltaic infrastructure, which occupies a considerably larger land area per unit of installed MW than wind turbines.

Figure 7 below shows the results for electricity generation. A first note is that PROENCAT2050 states that non-renewable electricity production will cease by 2050. Thus, the whole electricity will be produced with renewable sources.

Total GHG emissions will be 30% lower in 2050 than in 2020, considering the entire life cycle. However, in contrast to 2020, where most emissions were located at the production site (i.e., emissions from the combustion in non-renewable infrastructure), in the future, the impacts are distributed throughout the entire value chain, as renewable energies do not produce direct emissions during the use phase. Therefore, although we will be decreasing the total emissions, we will also be delocalizing them. On the other hand, WCP won't decrease but will be like those of today. Finally, we estimate that LOP might be 10 times greater in 2050.

FIGURE 7. GWP100, LOP AND WCP IMPACTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE (ABOVE) AND ELECTRICITY GENERATION (BELOW) IN 2020, 2030, 2040 AND 2050.

THE ROLE OF INCREMENTAL INFRASTRUCTURE

An interesting perspective is shown by analyzing the role that increments infrastructure plays in the energy transition. According to PROENCAT2050, the period between 2030 and 2040 is projected to witness a significant rise in renewable energy implementation. By 2040, it is expected that the deployment of renewable energy infrastructure will range between 2 and 2.7 times higher than that of 2030, particularly of onshore wind, rooftop photovoltaic,

and open-ground photovoltaic technologies deployment. Thus, as shown in Figure 8, the mentioned concerted implementation effort by 2040 is expected to result in greater incremental infrastructure impacts than those of any other of the projected decades. Moreover, the end-of-life of a significant number of MW of photovoltaic infrastructure is expected to occur in 2040 due to their approximate 30-year lifespan. On the other hand, wind infrastructure is projected to reach its peak of decommissioning in 2050 since these facilities have an anticipated lifespan of 20 years. Consequently, all implementation efforts made between 2020 and 2030 are expected to reach the end-of-life by 2050.

FIGURE 8. GWP100, LOP AND WCP OF THE INCREMENTAL INFRASTRUCTURE

IDENTIFYING POTENTIAL ENBIOS CONTRIBUTIONS

ENBIOS is further developed in the JUSTWIND4ALL project in both the technical input data on turbines and the assessment methods. First, development involves expanding the range and precision of turbine capabilities to accommodate the diversity found in the market and to keep pace with technological advancements. Additionally, consideration is being given to emerging technologies and practices that could play a significant role in the medium and long-term future of energy production, such as repowering turbines nearing the end of their useful life, floating offshore wind energy, and innovative concepts like airborne wind.

Second, there is a concerted effort to incorporate a broader range of social and environmental impacts into the analysis. This expanded perspective has the potential to provide stakeholders with more informed guidance when making decisions related to future energy planning. The barriers identified during the workshop serve as a reference for the further development of ENBIOS methods.

ONSHORE WIND

Table 5 summarizes the main drivers discussed for each of these barriers and the proposal of metrics or information that ENBIOS could include to help overcome them. In some cases, recommendations for metrics came up during the discussion whereas in others the proposal of metrics is ours. For some drivers, it is not possible to contribute with ENBIOS (marked as "--" in the table). Still, these drivers are included as they might be relevant for the wind labs within the project.

TABLE 5. SUMMARY OF METRIC DISCUSSION FOR ONSHORE WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA

BARRIER	DRIVERS	POTENTIAL ENBIOS CONTRIBUTION/METRICS
Territorial Imbalance	Lack of responsibility of cities	Energy demands of cities vs generating areas (usually rural)
	Lack of energy demand management	Identification of demands with highest impacts
	Lack of compensation mechanisms	--
Lack of strategic planning	Lack of integration of key environmental parameters in energy modelling	Soft link of ENBIOS and PROENCAT2050
		Including zoning beyond natura 2000 network including bird corridors and other GIS data.
		Overlap between Spanish and Catalan priority areas
Delay in administrative process	Long processing time resulting from incomplete reports	Identification of list of standard parameters.
	Lack of public register	--
Lack of awareness	Lack of data about the benefits of the energy transition for the general public	Environmental impacts of wind-based scenarios vs baseline scenario
Lack of participation	Lack of knowledge about actors affected	Regional environmental impacts vs energy benefits
	Lack of effective channels for participation	--
	Lack of a zoning of participation	--

Territorial imbalance. Catalunya has a general imbalance between the urban and rural areas and between the coastal vs the interior territories. Coastal areas are more populated, and their economies heavily rely on tourism, which comes with a significant increase of population and energy demands. Urban areas have a similar issue. This is particularly important in the metropolitan area of Barcelona, which is one of the most important demanding areas. Generation in urban areas finds great opposition due to the bigger population density and higher number of people affected by wind turbines. Due to the lack of awareness of the urban population about the impacts of generating electricity, there is little concern about how a reduction of the demand could benefit the region's energy system. The suggestion is that providing information on the impacts that the demand of energy of urban and/or coastal areas have and the places where part of these are located in the urban/interior areas will help overcome this barrier. This might also help with the design of compensation mechanism even though ENBIOS cannot directly contribute to this gap.

Lack of strategic planning. The PROENCAT2050 and the TIMES-Synergia energy models used to define scenarios for prospective planning in Spain and Catalunya do not include environmental parameters. As it happens with most energy system optimization models, this means that the optimization considers only constraints related to energy demands, costs and direct emissions at most. The proposal is to soft link ENBIOS with both energy models, producing dictionaries that connect activities in ENBIOS with categories of the energy models. A step further in this link would be the regionalization of ENBIOS according to the location of the foreseen wind parks, which would also contribute to meet some of the challenges posed by the drivers of the territorial imbalance.

Delay in administrative process. As mentioned above, one of the main barriers agreed by all parties was the lack of a common procedure for all wind energy projects. Projects in Catalunya are evaluated by the Spanish government (if more than 50 MW) or the Catalan government (less than 50 MW) according to environmental evaluation procedures that are not wind-specific and not even energy-specific. These specificities are only identified during

the administrative procedure and result if a request of changes to the project, delaying the authorization for installation. ENBIOS cannot contribute per se to the identification of a list of parameters that are specific to wind energy, but the elements identified in JUSTWIND4ALL and included in ENBIOS can support the standardization of parameters that can help administrations to speed up this process, avoiding the need for resubmissions. Another identified driver was the lack of dedicated public register, to which ENBIOS cannot contribute.

Lack of awareness and lack of participation. The last two barriers are very related to each other as lack of awareness can itself be a driver of the lack of participation. Among the many possible drivers that came up during discussion, those that are relevant for ENBIOS are related to the lack of knowledge about the urgency of the climate crisis and the benefits of wind energy in this context as well as the lack of information about who is affected by the projects. The proposal from ENBIOS is twofold. First, we could design a metric of impact saved as compared to a baseline scenario to help create awareness about the trade-offs of wind energy development. Second, a regionalization of this metric would be helpful in the identification of the population affected by energy projects.

DATA SOURCES

The participants mentioned during discussion the following sources of data that can be helpful when implemented the abovementioned changes in ENBIOS:

- Pla Territorial Sectorial per al Desenvolupament de les Energies Renovables a Catalunya (PLATER)
- Spanish energy Strategy
- UNFCCC reports showing effects of not transitioning for baseline comparison
- Majors' agreement for climate change transition in municipalities
- Statistics on installations (private, need to make public)

OFFSHORE WIND

Table 6 summarizes the main drivers discussed for each of these barriers and the proposal of metrics or information that ENBIOS could include to help overcome them. In some cases, recommendations for metrics came up during the discussion whereas in others the proposal of metrics is ours. For some drivers, it is not possible to contribute with ENBIOS (marked as "--" in the table). Still, these drivers are included as they might be relevant for the wind labs within the project.

Disintegration of regulations. The lack of a general regulatory framework that was a source of concern for onshore wind energy was also a concern for offshore wind energy parks. In the case of offshore this lack of integration is more accused as more administrations play a role in the evaluation and approval of the projects. An important point of discussion is related to the lack of scientific knowledge about effects of wind parks derived from models of marine dynamics adapted to the region. One of the effects that came up during discussion was the wake effect (the reduction of marine movements derived from turbines "stopping" the wind). Such models exist for the Northern Sea and are in development for the Catalan coastal dynamics, but their results are not yet validated and published. ENBIOS cannot contribute to the better modelling of the marine dynamic, but due to its foundations in socio-ecosystem dynamics can support the integration of indicators in a way that is more accessible to a range of administrations. In other words, the proposal would be to provide information from ENBIOS in a way that help administration dialogue to each other.

TABLE 6. SUMMARY OF METRIC DISCUSSION FOR OFFSHORE WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA

BARRIER	DRIVERS	POTENTIAL ENBIOS CONTRIBUTION/METRICS
Disintegration of regulation	Lack of marine models for Catalan coast	--
	Diversity of administrations involved in permitting	Including socio-ecological parameters that are relevant for more than one administration
Difficulty in grid connection	Concentration of grid connection of offshore parks	Assessment of grid needs and related impacts
Bird/wildlife protection	Difficult to understand impacts on bird and marine wildlife	--
	Lack of monitoring methods	--
	No integration of biodiversity in energy modelling	Definition of a new method for biodiversity in ENBIOS
Impact on tourism and fisheries	No integration of info on fisheries in environmental impacts	Identification of ENBIOS impacts related to Fishing and tourism activity
	Lack of knowledge about socio-ecological trade-offs	Local social impacts vs regional energy benefits
Lack of participation	Lack of best practices in citizen participation	**As onshore

Difficulties on grid connection. Offshore wind parks do not have the same network possibilities than onshore parks, as the number of potential entry points to the grid is more limited. Whereas the aim of ENBIOS is not to design energy systems, a proposal to help overcome this barrier is to help assess the impacts of different connectivity options for the local social-ecological system. This should be done by using the multi-level capabilities of the MuSIASEM module of ENBIOS, which must be further developed within the JUSTWIND4ALL project.

Lack of understanding of the true impacts over birds and wildlife. This is a broad barrier that came up from different perspectives during the discussion. One angle saw as driver the lack of actual information data about bird and wildlife impacts, like the concern about the lack of models of the marine dynamics commented above. Another, related, perspective highlighted the lack of monitoring methods to know if foreseen impacts are happening and which what intensity. Resulting from the above, there is little integration of biodiversity issues in modelling, which came as a big concern. The broad ENBIOS proposal would be to include a wind-specific biodiversity metric as part of the methods, which is a challenge due to the need of developing new semantics within the tool. Some ideas suggested the integration of biodiversity zoning maps in the regionalized ENBIOS assessment.

Impact on local activities. This is the most important barriers related to local development and the discussions highlighted the relevance of fisheries and tourism, concretely. Whereas understanding the full economic impacts is not a capability of ENBIOS, we can contribute a first assessment of the local environmental impacts that are related to fishery development (such as marine eutrophication) or tourism (such as effects over human health). The further step of assessing specific impacts (such as changes in the landscape) would require the development of new methods in ENBIOS. Another driver or concern related is the need to understand the trade-offs between local impacts and regional energy security as in the case of onshore wind parks.

Lack of participation. This is a shared issue with onshore wind implementation. However, during the discussion about offshore barriers and drivers, the component that was mostly highlighted did not relate to the lack of awareness of the general public and was rather

focused on the lack of proper channel. A proposal was raised of creating a guide of best practices for participation, which is not a contribution we can make, but is an expected result of the wind labs implemented within the project. ENBIOS can however contribute indicators that are semantically accessible, as commented before.

DATA SOURCES

The participants mentioned during discussion the following sources of data that can be helpful when implemented the abovementioned changes in ENBIOS:

- Global Fish Watch
- European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet)
- Information from the Marine Space Plans (POEMs)
- Information on marine ecological corridors from MITECO (RAMPE)
- Global Wind energy research Collaboration - Task 28
- Studies from fisheries or tourism industry associations

ACTION POINTS

The following list summarizes the results of the workshop as potential action points for the development of ENBIOS:

Regionalization of results

- Data on wind parks from the administration and private sector, but this is not so easily accessible.
- GIS information of potential impacts
 - Use the current zoning map of MITECO
 - Merge with zoning maps of Catalan Department of Territory

Inclusion of socio-ecological relations for local communities

- Need of modelling the impacts at the local level
- Connecting social dynamics with impacts, at least for fisheries and tourism
- Assessing trade-offs between local impacts and regional benefits of wind energy

Adding metrics for impacts on marine dynamics and biodiversity

- Connecting impacts like the wake effect with changes in biodiversity for offshore
- Improving zoning maps
 - Creating a variation of current zoning maps which adds to protected areas other relevant information like bird or marine corridors with information from RAMPE and EMODnet.

Holistic benefits of future wind energy deployment

- Metrics of comparison of impacts against current energy system impacts (net benefit)
- Identification of bottlenecks of highest change or highest impacts

Contributing to information transfer

- Improving visualization of results
- Development of a simplified way of communicating the metrics without reducing them to a single number
 - Identifying the different administrations involved

REFERENCES

- Aitken, M., McDonald, S., & Strachan, P. (2008). Locating 'power' in wind power planning processes: the (not so) influential role of local objectors. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 51(6), 777–799. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640560802423566>
- Banasiak, J., Najdawi, C., & Tiik, J. M. (2022). *Barriers and best practices for wind and solar electricity in the EU27 and UK. RES Policy Monitoring Database Final report*.
- Brown, J., & Isaacs, D. (2005). *The World Cafe: Shaping Our Futures Through Conversations That Matter* [Paperback]. 242. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_World_Caf%C3%A9.html?hl=es&id=Oqbjw1Z4_tYC
- Cortese, R. (2019). *Airborne Wind Energy: Development of a flying traction sensing system and integration of a wind monitoring system for extreme weather conditions*. Politecnico di Torino.
- Darmani, A., Arvidsson, N., Hidalgo, A., & Albors, J. (2014). What drives the development of renewable energy technologies? Toward a typology for the systemic drivers. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 38, 834–847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.023>
- Devine-Wright, P. (2005). Beyond NIMBYism: towards an integrated framework for understanding public perceptions of wind energy. *Wind Energy*, 8(2), 125–139. <https://doi.org/10.1002/WE.124>
- Devine-Wright, P. (2011). Public engagement with large-scale renewable energy technologies: breaking the cycle of NIMBYism. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 2(1), 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.1002/WCC.89>
- Dhingra, T., Sengar, A., & Sajith, S. (2022). A fuzzy analytic hierarchy process-based analysis for prioritization of barriers to offshore wind energy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 345, 131111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131111>
- Diógenes, J. R. F., Claro, J., Rodrigues, J. C., & Loureiro, M. V. (2020). Barriers to onshore wind energy implementation: A systematic review. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 60, 101337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101337>
- Duarte, R., García-Riazuelo, Á., Sáez, L. A., & Sarasa, C. (2022a). Analysing citizens' perceptions of renewable energies in rural areas: A case study on wind farms in Spain. *Energy Reports*, 8, 12822–12831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2022.09.173>
- Duarte, R., García-Riazuelo, Á., Sáez, L. A., & Sarasa, C. (2022b). Economic and territorial integration of renewables in rural areas: Lessons from a long-term perspective. *Energy Economics*, 110, 106005. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2022.106005>
- European Commission. (2022). REPowerEU Plan. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_3131.
- Friebe, C. A., Von Flotow, P., & Täube, F. A. (2014). Exploring technology diffusion in emerging markets – the role of public policy for wind energy. *Energy Policy*, 70, 217–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2014.03.016>
- Georgilakis, P. S. (2008). Technical challenges associated with the integration of wind power into power systems. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 12(3), 852–863. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2006.10.007>
- Haan, P., & Simmler, M. (2018). Wind electricity subsidies — A windfall for landowners? Evidence from a feed-in tariff in Germany. *Journal of Public Economics*, 159, 16–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2018.01.011>

- Hammons, T. J. (2008). Integrating renewable energy sources into European grids. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, 30(8), 462–475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJEPES.2008.04.010>
- ICAEN. (2020). *Balanç energètic de Catalunya, 2019*.
- ICAEN. (2022). *Prospectiva Energètica de Catalunya 2050 - PROENCAT 2050*.
- Iglesias, G., Del Río, P., & Dopico, J. Á. (2011). Policy analysis of authorisation procedures for wind energy deployment in Spain. *Energy Policy*, 39(7), 4067–4076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2011.03.033>
- Lloret, J., Turiel, A., Solé, J., Berdalet, E., Sabatés, A., Olivares, A., Gili, J. M., Vila-Subirós, J., & Sardá, R. (2022). Unravelling the ecological impacts of large-scale offshore wind farms in the Mediterranean Sea. *Science of The Total Environment*, 824, 153803. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2022.153803>
- Madrid-López, C., Nebot Medina, R., Martín, N., Talens Peiró, L., & Villalba-Méndez, G. (2022). *ENBIOS*. <https://pypi.org/project/enbios/>
- Martin, N., & Rice, J. (2015). Improving Australia's renewable energy project policy and planning: A multiple stakeholder analysis. *Energy Policy*, 84, 128–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2015.04.034>
- Maxwell, S. M., Kershaw, F., Locke, C. C., Conners, M. G., Dawson, C., Aylesworth, S., Loomis, R., & Johnson, A. F. (2022). Potential impacts of floating wind turbine technology for marine species and habitats. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 307, 114577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2022.114577>
- MITECO. (2020). *PLAN NACIONAL INTEGRADO DE ENERGÍA Y CLIMA*.
- Moragues-Faus, A. M., & Ortiz-Miranda, D. (2010). Local mobilisation against windfarm developments in Spanish rural areas: New actors in the regulation arena. *Energy Policy*, 38(8), 4232–4240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2010.03.053>
- Myrna, O., Odening, M., & Ritter, M. (2019). The Influence of Wind Energy and Biogas on Farmland Prices. *Land*, 8(1), 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/LAND8010019>
- OECD. (2012). *Linking Renewable Energy to Rural Development* (OECD Green Growth Studies). OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264180444-EN>
- Poggi, F., Firmino, A., & Amado, M. (2018). Planning renewable energy in rural areas: Impacts on occupation and land use. *Energy*, 155, 630–640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERGY.2018.05.009>
- Sacchi, R., Besseau, R., Pérez-López, P., & Blanc, I. (2019). Exploring technologically, temporally and geographically-sensitive life cycle inventories for wind turbines: A parameterized model for Denmark. *Renewable Energy*, 132, 1238–1250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.09.020>
- Smit, T., Junginger, M., & Smits, R. (2007). Technological learning in offshore wind energy: Different roles of the government. *Energy Policy*, 35(12), 6431–6444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2007.08.011>
- Subbulakshmi, A., Verma, M., Keerthana, M., Sasmal, S., Harikrishna, P., & Kapuria, S. (2022). Recent advances in experimental and numerical methods for dynamic analysis of floating offshore wind turbines — An integrated review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 164, 112525. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2022.112525>
- Süsser, D., al Rakouki, H., & Lilliestam, J. (2021). *The QTDIAN modelling toolbox – Quantification of social drivers and constraints of the diffusion of energy technologies. Deliverable 2.3. Sustainable Energy Transitions Laboratory (SENTINEL) project*. <https://doi.org/10.48481/IASS.2021.015>
- Süsser, D., Martín, N., Stavrakas, V., Gaschnig, H., Talens-Peiró, L., Flamos, A., Madrid-López, C., & Lilliestam, J. (2022). Why energy models should integrate social and environmental factors: Assessing user needs, omission impacts, and real-word accuracy

- in the European Union. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 92, 102775. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2022.102775>
- Süsser, D., Pickering, B., Chatterjee, S., Oreggioni, G., Stavrakas, V., & Lilliestam, J. (2021). *Integration of socio-technological transition constraints into energy demand and systems models. Deliverable 2.5. Sustainable Energy Transitions Laboratory (SENTINEL) project.* <https://doi.org/10.48481/IASS.2021.030>
- Toke, D., Breukers, S., & Wolsink, M. (2008). Wind power deployment outcomes: How can we account for the differences? *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 12, 1129–1147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2006.10.021>
- UNEF. (2021). *Informe anual 2021. Energía solar fotovoltaica, oportunidad para la sostenibilidad.*
- Vaughn, L. M., & Lohmueller, M. A. (2014). Calling all stakeholders: group-level assessment (GLA)-a qualitative and participatory method for large groups. *Evaluation Review*, 38(4), 336–355. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0193841X14544903>
- Wernet, G., Bauer, C., Steubing, B., Reinhard, J., Moreno-Ruiz, E., & Weidema, B. (2016). The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 21(9), 1218–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>
- WindEurope. (2022). *Wind energy in Europe. 2021 Statistics and the outlook for 2022-2026.*
- WindEurope. (2023). *Wind energy in Europe. 2022 Statistics and the outlook for 2023-2027.*
- Zografos, C., & Martinez-Alier, J. (2009). The Politics of Landscape Value: A Case Study of Wind Farm Conflict in Rural Catalonia. *Environment and Planning A*, 41(7), 1726–1744. <https://doi.org/10.1068/A41208>

ANNEX

WORKSHOP AGENDA AND FACILITATION GUIDE

9:30 - 10:00	REGISTRATION AND COFFEE
10:00 – 10:20	<p>WELCOME AND INTRO TO JUSTWIND4ALL PROJECT & WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB) and Andrzej Ceglarz (RGI)</i></p> <p>INTRODUCTION TO CATALUNYA’S REGIONAL WIND ENERGY <i>Francesc Xavier Rehues Estivill (Department of Territory - Catalunya)</i></p>
10:20 – 11:20	<p>INTERACTIVE EXPERT SESSION 1: IDENTIFYING BARRIERS OF WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA World café considering barriers of onshore and offshore wind energy <i>Andrzej Ceglarz and Amanda Schibline (RGI) to moderate</i></p>
11:20 - 11:35	COFFEE BREAK
11:35 – 12:30	<p>INTERACTIVE EXPERT SESSION 2: CLASSIFYING & PRIORITISING THE CO-CREATED BARRIERS Plenary exercise <i>Cristina Pérez Sánchez (UAB) to moderate</i></p>
12:30 – 13:15	<p>INTERACTIVE EXPERT SESSION 3: INFORMATION GAPS ON BARRIERS Plenary exercise <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB) to moderate</i></p> <p>KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM AFTERNOON SESSIONS <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB) and Andrzej Ceglarz (RGI)</i></p>
13:15 – 14:15	LUNCH BREAK
14:15 – 14:45	<p>INTRODUCTION TO ENERGY SYSTEM MODELS AND THE CATALUNYA ENERGY PLAN (PROENCAT) <i>Francesc Vidal (ICAEN)</i></p> <p>INTRODUCTION TO THE ENBIOS HOLISTIC IMPACT ASSESSMENT How ENBIOS has helped policymakers and visual aspects of ENBIOS <i>Cristina Madrid López and Miquel Sierra Montoya (UAB)</i></p>
14:55 – 15:20	<p>INTERACTIVE EXPERT DISCUSSION: ENERGY TRANSITION BARRIERS & MODELLING OPPORTUNITIES <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB)</i></p>
15:20 – 15:30	<p>KEY TAKEAWAYS OF WORKSHOP AND NEXT STEPS <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB)</i></p>

PARTICIPANT INSTITUTIONS

PRESENTATIONS

UAB Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

ENBIOS

Renewables Grid Initiative

JustWind4Catalunya Expert Workshop
Barriers of on - and offshore wind energy in Catalunya and the ENBIOS socio -environmental impact assessment

Funded by the European Union

Equip

ICTA Institut de Ciències i Tecnologia Industrial - UAB

sostenipira

Renewables Grid Initiative

Cristina Madrid, Cristina Pérez, Miquel Sierra, Andrzej Ceglaz, Amanda Schibline, Maria Cassinello, Ramir Soleymani, Nikki Harasta, Alex de Tomás

Funded by the European Union

Today's Agenda

9:30 - 10:00	REGISTRATION AND COFFEE
10:00 - 10:20	WELCOME AND INTRO TO JUSTWIND4ALL PROJECT & WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB) and Andrzej Ceglaz (ICTA)</i>
10:20 - 10:20	INTRODUCTION TO CATALUNYA'S REGIONAL WIND ENERGY <i>François Xavier Rehms Ederell (Department of Territory - Catalunya)</i>
10:20 - 11:20	INTERACTIVE EXPERT SESSION 1: IDENTIFYING BARRIERS OF WIND ENERGY IN CATALUNYA <i>World café considering barriers of onshore and offshore wind energy</i> <i>Andrzej Ceglaz and Amanda Schibline (IGI) to moderate</i>
11:20 - 11:35	COFFEE BREAK
11:35 - 12:30	INTERACTIVE EXPERT SESSION 2: CLASSIFYING & PRIORITISING THE CO-CREATED BARRIERS <i>Francis Xavier Rehms Ederell</i>
12:30 - 13:15	INTERACTIVE EXPERT SESSION 3: INFORMATION GAPS ON BARRIERS <i>Francis Xavier Rehms Ederell</i>
12:30 - 13:15	KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM AFTERNOON SESSIONS <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB) to moderate</i>
13:15 - 14:15	LUNCH BREAK
14:15 - 14:45	INTRODUCTION TO ENERGY SYSTEM MODELS AND THE CATALUNYA ENERGY PLAN (PROENCAT) <i>Francis Xavier Rehms Ederell</i>
14:15 - 14:45	INTRODUCTION TO THE ENBIOS HOLISTIC IMPACT ASSESSMENT <i>How ENBIOS has helped policymakers and visual aspects of ENBIOS</i> <i>Cristina Madrid López and Miquel Serra Moroteja (UAB)</i>
14:55 - 15:20	INTERACTIVE EXPERT DISCUSSION ENERGY TRANSITION BARRIERS & MODELLING OPPORTUNITIES <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB)</i>
15:20 - 15:30	KEY TAKEAWAYS OF WORKSHOP AND NEXT STEPS <i>Cristina Madrid López (UAB)</i>

REPowerEU: Accelerate clean energy transition

REPowerEU is the European Commission's plan to make Europe independent from Russian fossil fuels well before 2030, in light of Russia's invasion of Ukraine

510 GW of wind are required by 2030 to achieve the 69% share of renewable electricity modelled by the Commission. This would require average annual additions of 66 GW for wind

The REPowerEU Strategy signals the acceleration of large-scale renewable energy

What are the impacts on local communities and environment?

In reality, the implementation of the EU targets takes place at the regional and local level

50% of the EU target for 2030 is being met

47% of the EU target for 2050 is being met

43% of the EU target for 2050 is being met

43% of the EU target for 2050 is being met

JustWind4All

*JustWind4All aims to support the acceleration of on- and offshore wind energy through **just** and **effective** governance*

JustWind4All uses a trans- and interdisciplinary approach that combines social-ecological holistic impact assessment with techno-economic modelling to assess a variety of **social**, **environmental**, **technical**, and **economic** impacts and/or benefits to improve decision-making.

HOW? WHERE? WHAT are the EFFECTS? WHO BENEFITS?

JustWind4All addresses 4 Key Challenges

- Knowledge gaps**
How to assess the impacts of wind development, including social, environmental, technical and economic indicators?
- Justice deficit**
How to address disputes in a transparent way, resulting in a fair distribution of outcomes among stakeholders?

- Unsuitable policy frameworks**
How to foster more coherent policy frameworks taking into account the interrelations between different governance levels?
- Unlocking novel resources**
How to harness the full potential of wind energy making use of novel technologies, e.g., airborne wind energy?

JustWind4All's iterative, multi-method approach

How we work together

Who is JustWind4All?

Who is in the room today?

Government / Policy

NGO / CSO

Industry

Community / Citizen Group

Regional Planning for Wind in Catalunya

Francesc Xavier Belhues Estivill
Subdirecció General de Coordinació Urbanística

L'ENERGIA EÒLICA A CATALUNYA

L'ENERGIA EÒLICA A CATALUNYA

Context general

- El Consell Assessor per al Desenvolupament Sostenible (CADS) proposa assolir, per a 2030, un consum final d'energia renovable de com a mínim el 27% i un consum d'electricitat procedent de fonts renovables de com a mínim el 50% del total.
 - Aquesta producció s'ha distribuït entre les diferents fonts d'energia renovable, d'entre les quals, l'energia eòlica terrestre hauria de contribuir en 5.234 MW i l'energia eòlica marina en 1.000 MW.

L'ENERGIA EÒLICA A CATALUNYA

Implantació dels parcs eòlics terrestres

- En 2022 i 2023 han iniciat tràmit amb la Ponència d'Energies Renovables 41 projectes de parcs eòlics:
 - Sol·licituds totals a Catalunya: 1.085 MW / 191 aerogeneradors
 - Sol·licituds tramitació a través de la Generalitat: 501 MW / 93 aerogeneradors
 - Sol·licituds tramitació a través del Ministerio: 275 MW / 45 aerogeneradors
 - Sol·licituds autoritzades: 0 MW
 - Sol·licituds no autoritzades: 309 MW / 53 aerogeneradors
- Els expedients en tramitació, més el que disposàvem anteriorment, suma 2.152 MW, que és un 41% del que hauria de contribuir l'energia eòlica terrestre fins a 2030.

L'ENERGIA EÒLICA A CATALUNYA

Implantació dels parcs eòlics terrestres

- Aquestes instal·lacions però, s'han distribuït de manera poc proporcionada pel territori, concentrant-se en algunes comarques com ara el Segrià, o inclús en punts més concrets amb grans instal·lacions que generen un efecte acumulatiu amb fort impacte en el territori.
- El 52% de les sol·licituds s'encallen en les fases inicials del tràmit, en l'emissió de l'informe de suficiència i idoneïtat de la documentació presentada (art. 15.1). Aquelles que l'han passat han necessitat tramitar la documentació en una mitjana de 2,3 vegades.

L'ENERGIA EÒLICA A CATALUNYA

Context general

- La Llei 16/2017, de l'1 d'agost, del canvi climàtic vol contribuir a la transició cap a una societat on el consum de combustibles fòssils tendeixi a ser nul, amb un sistema energètic descentralitzat amb energies 100% renovables, fonamentalment de proximitat, amb l'objectiu d'aconseguir un model econòmic i energètic no dependent dels combustibles fòssils ni nuclears l'any 2050.
- El Decret Llei 16/2019, de 26 de novembre, de mesures urgents per a l'emergència climàtica i l'impuls a les energies renovables estableix un seguit de mesures per tal d'incrementar la generació d'energies d'origen renovable.

L'ENERGIA EÒLICA A CATALUNYA

Tramitació D.16/2019

L'ENERGIA EÒLICA A CATALUNYA

Implantació dels parcs eòlics terrestres

COMARCA	AEROGENERADORS				TOTAL
	EN SERVEI	EN TRAMITACIÓ	AUTORITZAT	NO AUTORITZ.	
Balears	161	4	0	0	165
Baixa Àlbr	161	1	0	0	162
Aranda	105	18	0	7	130
Catalunya	91	0	0	0	91
Comarca de Ribera	78	1	0	18	79
Segrià	18	55	0	10	73
Segura	68	9	0	0	77
Pla de l'Estany	21	41	0	18	62
Baix Camp	61	0	0	0	61
Alt Camp	44	0	0	0	44
Urgell	26	0	0	0	26
Alt Segura	10	0	0	0	10
Baix Segura	10	0	0	0	10
Alt Empordà	0	9	0	0	9
TOTAL	946	118	0	53	1067

L'ENERGIA EÒLICA A CATALUNYA

Qüestions

- Manca de planificació > PLATER
- Manca de qualitat paisatgística del projectes
- Rebuig social

Interactive Expert Session 1: Identifying Barriers of wind energy in Catalunya

Andrzej Ceglaz and Amanda Schibline (RGI)

Introduction to Energy System Models and the Catalunya Energy Plan (PROENCAT)

Francesc Vidal
Institut Català d'Energia (ICAEN)

PROSPECTIVA ENERGÈTICA DE CATALUNYA 2050 – PROENCAT 2050 –

29 de març de 2023

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia | Catalunya 2030 | #transicióenergètica

QUÈ ÉS LA PROENCAT 2050?

Prospectiva Energètica de Catalunya 2050 (PROENCAT 2050)

- La prospectiva energètica de Catalunya PROENCAT 2050 és el document que **fixa les visions de futur del sistema energètic** de Catalunya a llarg termini, amb l'objectiu de **facilitar la presa de decisions** en matèria de política energètica a mig i llarg termini.
- La PROENCAT 2050 defineix, a partir dels objectius energètics i ambientals fixats, les **estratègies** que cal implantar per assolir aquests objectius i fa una **previsió numèrica** de l'oferta i de la demanda energètica i avalua el seu impacte econòmic, social i mediambiental.

#transicióenergètica

PRINCIPIS VERTEBRADORS

- Assolir la neutralitat climàtica al 2050
- Abandonar model energètic fòssil-nuclear
- Aconseguir la sobirania energètica amb EERR
- Minimitzar l'ocupació del territori
- Apaperar ciutadans i empreses i impulsar la transformació social
- Desenvolupar una economia pròspera, moderna, competitiva i circular
- Posar en primer lloc l'eficiència energètica
- No deixar ningú enrere
- Aplicar el principi de neutralitat tecnològica cost-eficient
- Assegurar un subministrament energètic assequible i segur
- Dissenyar un nou sistema elèctric i el seu funcionament
- Apostar decididament per la recerca, desenvolupament i innovació

#transicióenergètica

PRINCIPALS RESULTATS

Repartiment per formes d'energia

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

PRINCIPALS RESULTATS

GENERACIÓ D'ENERGIA ELÈCTRICA

Evolució de la potència renovable instal·lada per tecnologies (MW)

	2020	2030	2040	2050
Hidràulica	1.825,3	1.825,8	1.825,8	1.825,8
Eòlica terrestre	1.271,1	5.234,2	16.939,0	23.136,0
Eòlica marina	0,0	1.000,0	1.500,0	3.500,0
Fotovoltaica teulades	249,7	2.185,2	7.275,9	11.144,4
Fotovoltaica altres	0,0	512,6	2.026,6	2.614,0
Fotovoltaica terra	94,8	4.458,8	13.129,0	19.394,3
Altres ¹	116,7	191,8	270,9	247,4
TOTAL	3.557,6	16.408,4	42.967,2	61.861,8
Emmagatzematge	534,0	2.234,0	4.034,0	7.234,0
Hidràulica de bombament	534,0	2.234,0	4.034,0	7.234,0
Bateries	0,0	200,0	600,0	3.500,0

¹ Altres inclou: RESU renovable, cogeneració renovable, bioga, biomassa forestal i agrícola i solar termoelèctrica

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

PRINCIPALS RESULTATS

GENERACIÓ D'ENERGIA ELÈCTRICA

Contribució de les fonts energètiques en la producció d'energia elèctrica renovable

	2020	2030	2040	2050
Hidràulica	59,6%	12,6%	5,1%	3,6%
Eòlica	30,1%	51,6%	51,0%	51,1%
Eòlica terrestre	30,1%	39,6%	43,8%	39,6%
Eòlica marina	0,0%	11,6%	7,1%	11,4%
Fotovoltaica	5,5%	33,2%	42,4%	44,2%
Fotovoltaica teulades i altres	3,7%	11,0%	15,5%	16,4%
Fotovoltaica terra	1,8%	22,2%	27,0%	27,8%
Altres ¹	4,8%	2,5%	1,5%	1,0%

(1) Altres inclou: RESU renovable, cogeneració renovable, bioga, biomassa forestal i agrícola i solar termoelèctrica
(2) Instal·lacions fotovoltaiques que ocupen teulades o espais ja urbanitzats. No es correspon amb les instal·lacions d'autoconsum, que poden estar ubicades també a terra

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

PRINCIPALS RESULTATS

GENERACIÓ D'ENERGIA ELÈCTRICA

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

PRINCIPALS RESULTATS

GENERACIÓ D'ENERGIA ELÈCTRICA

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

INVERSIONS NECESSÀRIES PER A LA TRANSICIÓ ENERGÈTICA

- Les **inversions associades** a la PROENCAT 2050 per a la producció d'electricitat, la utilització d'energies renovables tèrmiques, el reforçament de les xarxes elèctriques de transport i distribució i per a mesures de millora de l'estalvi, i l'eficiència energètica són de **84.361 M€**.
- Les **inversions en sistemes de generació d'electricitat representen la major part** de les inversions necessàries, amb un **61%**. Les inversions en estalvi i eficiència energètica també són molt rellevants, ja que representen quasi el 18% del total. No obstant, cal tenir en compte les dificultats per estimar aquestes inversions.

Inversions en generació d'electricitat	51.511 M€
Inversions en infraestructures de la xarxa elèctrica	13.256 M€
Inversions en estalvi i eficiència	15.000 M€
Inversions en utilització de renovables tèrmiques	4.594 M€
TOTAL	84.361 M€

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

PRINCIPALS RESULTATS - CONCLUSIONS

GENERALS

- Es possible assolir la **neutralitat climàtica** relacionada amb l'energia l'any 2050.
- Un sistema energètic català **100% renovable**, autòcton, eficient i competitiu és possible.
- El **tancament de les centrals nuclears** en els terminis acordats és possible.
- Es **desacoblarà el creixement econòmic del consum d'energia** i es reduirà el consum d'energia per càpita d'una manera dràstica.
- S'aplica el **principi de neutralitat tecnològica cost-eficient** en l'àmbit de l'energia, el medi ambient i els materials.
- Es produirà una **força electrificació** de l'economia.
- Disposar d'un sector elèctric **100% renovable no és suficient** per assolir la neutralitat climàtica.
- La **transició energètica tindrà impactes**, però molt **menors que els beneficis**.
- Es produirà una **ocupació addicional moderada del territori**.
- Es manté l'objectiu d'assolir la **sobria alimentària** i de respectar al màxim la **biodiversitat**.
- Els **ciutadans** i les **empreses** seran **protagonistes** de la transició energètica.

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

PRINCIPALS RESULTATS - CONCLUSIONS

EN L'ÀMBIT DEL SISTEMA ELÈCTRIC

- Canvi de paradigma** en el funcionament del sistema elèctric.
- Necessitat d'una **anàlisi horària** del sistema elèctric català.
- La **generació distribuïda** d'energia elèctrica a petita i mitjana escala **no és suficient** per cobrir la demanda.
- El preu de la generació d'energia elèctrica serà **competitiu** a mig i llarg termini (2030-2050).
- Cal desenvolupar un **nou mercat elèctric**.
- Implantació generalitzada de l'**acumulació d'energia elèctrica** amb bateries.
- Necessitat de disposar de nous sistemes de **bombament hidroelèctric** i de mantenir el parc hidroelèctric actual.
- Es proposa una solució al repte de l'**acumulació estacional d'electricitat**.
- Importància de les **interconnexions** amb els sistemes elèctrics veïns.
- Serà necessari **ampliar i reforçar les xarxes elèctriques**.

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

MAIN RESULTS - CONCLUSIONS

GENERAL

- It is possible to achieve energy-related **climate neutrality** by 2050.
- A **100% renewable**, efficient and competitive Catalan energy system is possible.
- The **closure of nuclear power plants** within the agreed deadlines is possible.
- Economic growth** will be decoupled from energy consumption and per capita energy consumption will be drastically reduced.
- The **principle of cost-efficient technological neutrality** is applied in the field of energy, the environment and materials.
- A **strong electrification** of the economy will occur.
- Having a **100% renewable electricity sector** is not enough to achieve climate neutrality.
- The energy transition will have **impacts**, but much **smaller than the benefits**.
- There will be **moderate additional occupation** of the territory.
- The objective to achieve **food sovereignty** and maximum respect for **biodiversity** is maintained.
- Citizens and companies** will be **protagonists** in the energy transition.

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

MAIN RESULTS - CONCLUSIONS

IN THE FIELD OF THE ELECTRICAL SYSTEM

- Paradigm change** in the operation of the electrical system.
- Need for an **hourly analysis** of the Catalan electricity system.
- Small and medium-scale **distributed generation** of electrical energy is **not sufficient** to meet demand.
- The price of electricity generation will be **competitive** in the medium and long term (2030-2050).
- A **new electricity market** must be developed.
- Generalized implementation of the **electrical energy storage** with batteries.
- Need to have new **hydroelectric pumping systems** and to maintain the current hydroelectric park.
- A solution to the challenge of the **seasonal accumulation of electricity** is proposed.
- Importance of **interconnections** with neighboring electrical systems.
- It will be necessary to **expand and strengthen the electric grid**.

#transicióenergètica

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia Catalunya 2030

Introduction to ENBIOS Holistic Impact Assessment

Dr. Cristina Madrid López & Miquel Sierra Montoya
UAB

PROENCAT2050 Analysis

PROENCAT2050 projections

1. How did we analyze the environmental impacts?

- Impacts of **cumulative power** (total infrastructure)
- Impacts of **newly installed power** (new infrastructure)
 - Expected increase
 - Replacement of end-of-life technologies
- Impacts of **electricity generation**

2. Level of detail of technologies and assumptions

- Wind power** <1 MW, 1-3 MW, >3 MW (only some will be installed of this size from 2030)
- Other photovoltaics and land** they have considered all on the ground
- Photovoltaic roofs** yes differentiated between mono and polycrystalline plates
- Hydraulics** Yes differentiated between reservoir and minihydraulics
- Others** Yes considered biogas, renewable MSW, biomass and thermoelectric solar (with data taken from the Balance Energy in Catalonia 2020)
- Storage** Excluded from analysis

Results of the PROENCAT2050 (February 4, 2022)

Current situation (2020). Infrastructure

Main results

- Renewable installed infrastructure has more GHG emissions than non-renewable.
- This is largely due to hydro power plants.
- Much of the impact is due to the production of cement.

What are we trying to improve?

- Resolution of wind technologies
- Spatial resolution
 - Technologies
 - Impacts

What are the greenhouse gas emissions of current electricity production infrastructures (installed power) considering the entire supply chain?

Current situation (2020). Impact of the generation

Main results

- Nonrenewable generation represents more than 95% of emissions throughout the entire life cycle.
- Co-generation and combined cycle concentrate most of the emissions far from nuclear power.
- Among the renewables, hydro power is the one that generates the most emissions.

What are we trying to improve?

- Decoupling impacts on the territory from the rest of the supply chain.

What are the greenhouse gas emissions of current annual electricity production considering the entire supply chain?

Future total infrastructure impacts

Main results

- The impacts of the projected renewable infrastructure will be large (more than doubled in the first decade) compared to today.

Future total infrastructure impacts

Main results

- The impacts of the projected renewable infrastructure will be large (more than doubled in the first decade) compared to today.
- Photovoltaic infrastructure deployment leads all the impact categories, even though the power deployed is less than that of wind power.

Future total infrastructure impacts

Impact per MW built

Key results

- Although projections envisage the Catalan energy system reaching climate neutrality in 2050, it must be considered that there will be emissions associated with the other phases of the technologies' life cycle beyond use.

Impacts of the new infrastructure

Key results

- The projected renewable implementation effort between 2030 and 2040 makes it the most impactful decade.
- This same decade coincides with the peak of installed power that will reach its end of life and will have to be replaced or re-powered.

Impacts of electricity generation

Key results

- Although projections envisage the Catalan energy system reaching climate neutrality in 2050, it must be considered that there will be emissions associated with the other phases of the technologies' life cycle beyond use.

Impacts of electricity generation

Key results

1. Although projections envisage the Catalan energy system reaching climate neutrality in 2050, it must be considered that there will be emissions associated with the other phases of the technologies' life cycle beyond use.
2. Most of the renewable impacts will be produced by photovoltaic energy, except in the case of water consumption potential, where hydro electricity will continue to lead.

Other projects

PNIEC. Current situation (2015). Electric

What are the greenhouse gas emissions throughout the life cycle of electricity production?

PNIEC. Electricity generation impacts

seeds Portugal. Connection with optimization models

- Scenario analysis of an energy optimization model (Callope).
- The model generates 260+ near -optimal solutions for two regions in Portugal to achieve climate neutrality by 2050.
- 6 environmental indicators are analyzed with ENBIOS.
- The scenario with the best results for all 6 indicators compared to impacts of the electricity generation in 2020 is selected.
- The most favorable scenario contemplates 85.4% of on-shore wind energy.

Thank you for attending!

FOLLOW US:

- @JustWind4All
- @JustWind4All

JUSTWIND4ALL is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (ECIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them (Grant Agreement 101023936).

PICTURES OF WORKSHOP'S MATERIALS

OFF

DRIVERS	INFO/DATA
<p>Regulation</p> <p>Regulation of forest land use in an ecosystem with an ecological perspective</p>	<p>Provision of plan Caters surfacica Visor web informat</p> <p>REGULATORY MEASURES PROPOSED BY MHA</p> <p>IMPACT of these measures on regional ecosystems need to be low possible Solutions</p> <p>TSO ??</p>
<p>Connection to Grid</p> <p>Plan for grid & other infrastructure</p>	<p>PROVISION of energy services to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p>
<p>Bird/wildlife Protection</p> <p>Knowledge about bird habitat and feeding areas</p>	<p>CLAPS</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p>
<p>Impact on tourism, fisheries</p> <p>Knowledge about tourism and fisheries impact</p>	<p>CONNECTION to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p>
<p>Lack of Public Participation</p> <p>Participatory and consultative</p>	<p>CONNECTION to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p> <p>CONNECTION to the grid</p>

ON

DRIVERS	INFO/DATA
<p>TERR IMBALANCE OPPOSITION</p> <p>Terrestrial ecosystems management plan</p> <p>TERRESTRIAL ECOSYSTEMS MANAGEMENT PLAN</p>	<p>PERIODIC ASSESSMENT OF TERRESTRIAL ECOSYSTEMS MANAGEMENT PLAN</p> <p>PERIODIC ASSESSMENT OF TERRESTRIAL ECOSYSTEMS MANAGEMENT PLAN</p> <p>PERIODIC ASSESSMENT OF TERRESTRIAL ECOSYSTEMS MANAGEMENT PLAN</p>
<p>LACK STRATEGIC PLANNING</p> <p>Lack of knowledge integrated in energy modeling</p>	<p>Bird corridor maps exist</p> <p>Species / Habitats Energy modeling Natura 2000</p> <p>PLATER</p>
<p>LACK OF AWARENESS</p> <p>Local Municipal initiatives plans cc.</p>	<p>Discrepancy between regional and local plans</p> <p>Discrepancy between regional and local plans</p>
<p>ADMIN PROC.</p> <p>Check loop</p>	<p>Discrepancy between regional and local plans</p> <p>Discrepancy between regional and local plans</p>
<p>LACK PRACTIC.</p> <p>Check loop</p>	<p>Discrepancy between regional and local plans</p> <p>Discrepancy between regional and local plans</p>

ENBIOS SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

TABLE 7 FUTURE SCENARIOS ASSUMPTIONS

Energy type	Assumption	Assumption basis	Data source
Wind onshore	All new turbines of >3MW.	Newly installed turbines are 4MW or higher since 2021 in Europe and Spain.	(WindEurope, 2022, 2023)
Photovoltaic rooftop	All new photovoltaics monocrystalline.	Market trends.	(UNEF, 2021)
Other renewables	No increase in residues technologies.	General governments proposals to reduce residues generation	-

TABLE 8. FUTURE SCENARIOS DECOMMISSION CALCULATION METHODS

ENERGY TYPE	CALCULATION METHOD	LIFETIME	DATA SOURCE
WIND ONSHORE	HISTORICAL RECORD OF WIND TURBINE INSTALLATIONS IN CATALUNYA FROM 1990 TO 2010.	20	(ICAEN, 2020; SACCHI ET AL., 2019; WERNET ET AL., 2016)
PHOTOVOLTAICS	HISTORICAL RECORD OF PHOTOVOLTAIC INSTALLATIONS IN CATALUNYA FROM 1990 TO 2010. PROPORTION OF 1MW OPEN GROUND FOR EVERY 3MW ROOFTOP	30	(WERNET ET AL., 2016)
OTHER RENEWABLES	POWER SHARE FROM 2020 MAINTAINED FOR ALL TECHNOLOGIES.	NOT CONSIDERED	-

Dendrogram

FIGURE 9 HIERARCHICAL STRUCTURING OF THE ENERGY SYSTEM INSIDE ENBIOS (DENDROGRAM)

**Funded by
the European Union**

JUSTWIND4ALL IS FUNDED BY THE EUROPEAN UNION. VIEWS AND OPINIONS EXPRESSED ARE HOWEVER THOSE OF THE AUTHOR(S) ONLY AND DO NOT NECESSARILY REFLECT THOSE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION OR THE EUROPEAN CLIMATE, INFRASTRUCTURE AND ENVIRONMENT EXECUTIVE AGENCY (CINEA). NEITHER THE EUROPEAN UNION NOR THE GRANTING AUTHORITY CAN BE HELD RESPONSIBLE FOR THEM (GRANT AGREEMENT 101083936).